

Colhelper- Access interface to the MNHN collections: Study of the targeted functionalities for ELViS, European Loans and Visiting System

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INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the SYNTHESYS+ Join Research Activities (JRA) work package is to develop ELViS - an integrated European Loans and Visits System to support requests for access to natural science collections and DoD services of DiSSCo RI institutions.

Within the JRA, the Task 6.1 (Structure & design of system: Design system architecture to align with future DiSSCo requirements) is concerned with the design of a user interface (UI) that will form the basis of the DiSSCo core UI.

This design process draws in particular on current experiences with similar systems such as the Colhelper, an online collection access service created and used by the MNHN since 2006.

Within this framework, the MNHN has designed a study of the functionality of Colhelper to feed into the JRA1 working group on the future functionality of the ELViS UI.

The document "Colhelper: Study of the targeted functionalities for ELViS, European Loans and Visiting System" was elaborated by a study of the existing Colhelper interface and by feedback from users (Dispatcher and Collection Manager) of the MNHN.

COLHELPER FUNCTIONALITIES

1 - What is Colhelper and general principles

1.1 - What is Colhelper?

Colhelper is an application developed by the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN) in 2006 that allows to make requests to the Museum's collections and to have a collaborative tool to process these requests accessible to collection managers. It is a single-entry point for scientists from all over the world. It is composed of two parts: a "front office" for requesters and a "back office" allowing requests to be managed by collection managers.

Since 2006, 11417 visits have been recorded in Colhelper, 8742 loans and 2043 sampling requests. It should be noted that the use of Colhelper has been gradual over the years. It has required a great deal of communication with users with a view to generalising the tool. The level of obedience varies according to the type of request.

Dispatcher	Manager	Requester
23	341	13071

Number of roles registered in Colhelper to date

Year	Loans	Sampling	Visit	Exchange	Images
2020	275	116	340	2	389
2019	593	337	916	8	519
2018	642	261	1 036	1	451
2017	786	186	1 119	3	421
2016	750	218	953	1	395
2015	689	182	1 014	3	282
2014	746	187	910	4	282
2013	773	163	945	2	303
2012	758	106	864	13	264
2011	732	92	819	7	277
2010	633	77	814	4	260
2009	723	59	891	3	259
2008	453	54	634	3	185
2007	189	5	162	2	72
Sum	8 742	2 043	11 417	56	4 359

Extensions	Donation, Bequest, Sales	Exhibition	Collection questions	Mouldings, Preparation, Restoration	Total requests
30	4	24	154	3	1 337
31	24	29	213	6	2 676
20	7	35	227	1	2 681
15	15	55	217	4	2 821
47	20	50	223	2	2 659
83	13	48	161	3	2 478
36	17	70	186	4	2 442
10	35	65	210	26	2 532
26	36	53	189		2 309
13	18	51	167		2 176
6	29	74	196		2 093
19	19	63	194		2 230
24	7	29	153		1 542
3	6	12	34		485
363	250	658	2 524	49	30 461

Number of requests processed in colhelper

This system can manage several types of request:

- 1 – **Loan of specimen:** Request for loan of specimens.
- 2 – **Loan of specimen with sampling authorization:** Request for loan with samplings.
- 3 – **Loan extension:** Request for loan extension.
- 4 – **Sampling:** Request for specimen sampling.
- 5 – **Visit:** Request for visit and consult the collections.
- 6 – **Exchange:** Request for exchange material.
- 7 – **Image:** Request for specimen digitalization.
- 8 – **Donation, bequest and sale:** Request for donations, bequests and sales of collections or specimens.
- 10 – **Exhibition:** Request for loan for exhibition.
- 11 – **Collection question:** Request to ask questions about a collection or specimens.
- 12 – **Moulding, preparation, restoration:** Request for moulding, preparation and restoration of specimen related to "Ateliers Naturalia".

1.2 - General principles

The application must follow the following principles:

- 1 - A request is always under the responsibility of a single collection manager.
- 2 - By default, the request is assigned to the "dispatcher" of the service concerned.
- 3 - Responsibility for a request may vary during the processing of the request. The collection manager in charge of the request may pass on this responsibility to another collection manager.
- 4 - Only the collection manager in charge of the request can "accept" or "refuse" the request.
- 5 - Not all collections accept all types of requests. Each collection will have to define the types of requests it accepts. A list will be proposed to the user according to the chosen collection.
- 6 - A request has a state throughout its life cycle. These statuses are:
 - **In progress:** The request is being processed.
 - **Pending:** The request is pending and is awaiting a response (from the requester or another collection manager).
 - **To be prepared:** The request has been accepted and is to be prepared.
 - **Close or resolved:** The request is closed.

The different actions of the collection managers (see Chapter 4.7 - Actions on requests) can change the status of the request and some actions are only possible depending on the status of the request.

1.3 - Definition of terms

A **request** is a demand made by a requester with the front office of Colhelper.

A **requester** is a user who makes a request with the front office of Colhelper.

A **supervisor** is a permanent member of the institution that support the request, or, in the case of non-institutional requesters, a person who acts as sponsor.

A **dispatcher** is a collection manager who receives all requests for a service and assigns the request to another collection manager to be process.

A **collection manager** is a person from collections who can process requests.

2 - Organisation of services and managers

The prioritisation and classification of collection and the assignment of managers in Colhelper correspond to the organisation of the MNHN's internal services.

It has been important to introduce in the system a certain flexibility in this prioritisation because of the evolution of the internal services within the MNHN throughout its history. Thus, the notion of service was introduced.

2.1 - Services

Services are entities which stand for a collection or a set of collections. A service can have service children.

Services are defined by the following information:

- Name of the service
- Parent service: Higher level service
- The person in charge of the service (optional)
- Address (2 lines)
- Postcode
- City
- Country
- Phone
- Fax

With this architecture, it is possible to build a tree of services where requester can navigate to find the service concerned by its request.

For example, the MNHN have a service called "Botany" which contains two services "Vascular plants (with ferns)" and "Cryptogams (except ferns)". The "Cryptogams (except ferns)" service contains four services "Lichens", "Mushrooms", "Algae" and "Bryophyta". There are three levels of services.

2.2 - Collections

Collections are entities which stand for naturalist collections. Each collection has a name and belongs to a service.

Collections are defined by the following information:

- Name of the collection
- Related service

With this architecture, several collections could belong to a service.

2.3 - Collection managers

Collection managers are defined by the following information:

- Last name, first name
- Email
- Function (French, English)
- Signature (email)
- Related service

Collection managers must have an account to be authenticated with a login and password.

Collection managers must belong to a service.

A service can have several collection managers.

2.4 - Roles

Collection managers have roles:

- Dispatcher: coordinator of a service
- Request manager: Ability to handle a request

The dispatcher is a collection manager who receives all requests concerning a service (first person in charge of the request). The dispatcher will assign requests to others collection managers to handle them and have a role of coordinator. There is only one dispatcher by service.

3 - Front office for requesters

Colhelper's front office is the main entrance for users to the MNHN's collections, as well as the managers of the targeted collections. Access link: <http://colhelper.mnhn.fr>

Colhelper is in French and almost entirely accessible in English. Some features still need to be translated into English.

To submit a request, the user must have an account accessible with a unique username and password.

3.1 - Create a user account

In order to make a request to the collections of the MNHN, a user must create an account in order to provide information about his identity and possibly the institution to which he belongs and on a supervisor. This information may be important if a specimen loan has been granted to a requester and the specimen(s) have not been returned before the loan's due date. Collection managers can then contact the institution or the manager/supervisor directly to request the return of the specimens.

The registration process is divided into several steps:

- 1 – Choosing a country.
- 2 – Choosing an institution. If the requesters are individuals, they can indicate that they do not belong to an institution and can go directly to step 4.
- 3 – If the requester's institution is not registered in the database, they can add their institution by filling in the institution information (e.g. 3.1.1). A new entity "institution" is created.
- 4 – Choosing a supervisor or a sponsor if requester is an individual.
- 5 – If the requester's supervisor/sponsor is not registered in the database, requesters can create a new "supervisor" entity by filling in the requested information (e.g. 3.1.2).
- 6 – Fill in the user's identity information

Flowchart: Creating a user account

3.1.1 - Information about institutions

The information about an institution are:

- Name of the institution
- Acronym (e.g. MNHN)
- Address (4 fields)
- Postcode
- City
- Country

3.1.2 - Information about supervisors

The information about a supervisor are:

- Last name, first name
- Function
- Email
- Phone
- Address (4 fields)
- Postcode
- City
- Country

3.1.3 - Information about requester identity

The information about requester identity are:

- Last name, initials (or middle name), first name
- Email
- Signature: This signature will be used in email sent to the requester.
- Address (5 fields)
- Postcode
- City
- Country
- Phone
- Fax
- Activity (list of choices): Ecology, journalism, systematic, other
- Status (list of choices): Amateur, professional, researcher, doctoral student, student, journalist, other

3.2 - Submitting a request

Users, having a user account, can make a request. This request takes place in several steps:

Flowchart: Submitting a request

- Collections scientifiques
 - Géologie
 - Paléontologie
 - Botanique
 - Plantes vasculaires
 - Cryptogames (sauf fougères)
 - Vertébrés
 - Arthropodes terrestres
 - Invertébrés non arthropodes terrestres
 - Ethnobotanique
 - Anthropologie
 - Préhistoire
 - Végétaux vivants
 - Protistes
 - Base I2AF
 - Ethnologie
 - Ateliers Naturalia
 - Ressources Biologiques et Cellules
- Proposition de don/leg/vente
- Exposition

1 - Choosing a collection or type of request.

This choice is made using a hierarchical tree whose root contains the scientific collections, proposals for donations/bequests/sales and requests linked to an exhibition. The last two requests are not linked to particular collections or concern different services and redirects the user to step 4 directly.

List: choosing a collection or type of request

2 - Choose a type of request from a list.

Once the collection has been selected, users are referred to a choice among several types of requests specific to the collections

CHOICE OF REQUEST TYPE

If many request types are relevant, please submit different requests

- Loan of specimens
- Loan extension
- Sampling
- Exchange
- Images
- Visit
- Questions about the collection

Type of request form

Collection
Ensemble botanique

Type of request
Loan of specimens

Object

Usage

Text

Default request form

3 - Depending on the type of request, general conditions are presented to the users. The user is obliged to tick a box indicating that he has read the general terms and conditions and accepts them (see Appendix A - E).

4 - Fill in a form describing the request and add one or more attachments if necessary.

For all requests, the users must fill in the following information: Subject of the request, Usage, detail (body of the request).

Collection
Ensemble botanique

Type of request
Loan extension

Object

Usage

Text

Loan number
Reference number of the loan request to be extended

Extension date
Desired date for loan extension

If the request is a loan extension request, the users must enter the loan number (Reference number of the loan request to be extended) and the extension date (Desired date for loan extension).

Form for loan extension

Collection
Ensemble botanique

Type of request
Sampling

Object

Usage

Text

For commercial use

If the request is for a sampling request, the users must indicate whether the sample will be used for commercial purposes.

Form for sampling request

Collection
Ensemble botanique

Type of request
Visit

Object

Usage

Text

Start date

End date

If the request is a visit request, the users must indicate the start and end date of the visit.

Form for visit request

5 – Submit the request. An email is sent to the “dispatcher”. The request is then to be managed in the Colhelper back office.

4 - Back office for collection managers

Colhelper's back office is the interface (web application) for registered collection managers to handle requests made to the collections and the MNHN institution. The application provides a workflow to handle request and a system for managing past and current requests. To date, 14 years of activities have been archived in Colhelper.

4.1 - Homepage

The homepage is the entry point of the back office for collection managers. They can see in different tabs: the requests under their responsibility and the requests in which they participated.

Several tabs are displayed:

- The list of "In progress" requests
- The list of "Pending" requests
- The list of "To be prepared" requests
- The list of "Close" requests (history)
- The search form: the collection manager can see all requests based on criteria.
-

4.2 - Advanced search form

An advanced search form allows to search for one or more requests based on several criteria:

- Request number
- Requester (who submitted the request)
- Institution
- Type of request (drop-down list). If the type of request is a loan, it is possible to select ongoing loans and/or expired loans (checkboxes)
- Collection acronym. This allows to have a list of loan requests for a collection
- Inventory number of a specimen. This allows to have a list of loan requests for a specimen
- Status of request: all, accepted, refused, open (radio buttons)
- Collection to which the request was addressed (drop-down list)
- Manager who participated in the processing of the request (drop-down list)
- Request accepted between a start date and/or an end date
- Request made between a start date and/or an end date

Request number <input type="text"/>	Requester <input type="text" value="▼"/>
Type of request <input type="text" value="▼"/>	Institution <input type="text" value="▼"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Loans in progress <input type="checkbox"/> Expired loans	
Loans	Request status
Collection acronym <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/> all <input type="radio"/> accepted <input type="radio"/> refused <input type="radio"/> open
Inventory number <input type="text"/>	
Collection to which the request was addressed <input type="text" value="▼"/>	Manager involved in the processing of the request <input type="text" value="▼"/>
Request accepted after <input type="text"/>	Request submitted after (JJ/MM/AAAA) <input type="text"/>
and before <input type="text"/>	and before <input type="text"/>
<input type="button" value="Recherche"/>	

Advanced search form

A list of requests that matches the selected criteria is then displayed.

4.3 - List of requests

The list of requests is shown as a table containing the following columns:

- Request ID: a link to access the request page
- Requester last name et first name: a link to access the requester page
- Institution: a link to access the institution sheet
- Creation date
- Last action on the request
- Type of request
- Subject of the request
- Collection concerned

En cours (10)	En attente (5)	À préparer (2)	Rechercher	Préférences
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ID	Nom du demandeur	Institution	Date de création	Dernière action	Type de demande	Objet	Collection
350500	Doe, John	University of Turku (TUR)	29/09/2020	Transmission	Emprunt de spécimen	Centipedes (Myriapoda: Chilopoda: Scolopendromorpha)	Ensemble Arthropodes terrestres
250655	Doe, John	Muséum Nat. Hist. Nat. - PARIS (MNHN)	21/09/2020	Acceptation	Emprunt de spécimen	Modification demande n°145116	Reptiles & Amphibiens
249853	Doe, John	Swedish Museum of Natural History	14/09/2020	Acceptation	Emprunt de spécimen	Specimens of Anisopappus (Asteraceae-Athroismeae)	Ensemble Botanique
157842	Doe, John	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa - Wellington	10/07/2020	Acceptation	Prélèvement	Tissue clips from available molecular-grade Haliotis speci	Ensemble Invertébrés n.a.t.
138074	Doe, John	Université de Neuchâtel (NEU)	21/08/2020	Suivi	Visite	Visite de l'Herbier Rousseau	Ensemble Botanique
138004	Doe, John	Università degli Studi di Ferrara	07/08/2020	Acceptation	Visite	Demande d'accès aux collections d'anatomie comparée	Mammifères, Oiseaux & Anat. Comp.
126555	Doe, John	Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso do Sul - Campo Grande	28/06/2019	Refus	Exposition	Paleontology - Kozłowski Collection – trilobites	Grande Galerie

List of requests / search

4.4 - The requester page

When the requester's name is clicked, a page appears containing all the information about the requester and these requests.

Requester page

4.4.1 - Presentation of the requester

The requester's information is as follows:

- Last name, first name
- Email
- Phone, fax
- Address, postcode, city, country
- Institution
- Supervisor
- Activity: Ecology, journalist, systematic, other
- Status: Amateur, professional, researcher, PhD student, student, journalist, other

This gives the manager all the information necessary to identify and contact him if necessary.

4.4.2 - Loans returned by the requester

This section shows a table containing loans granted to that person, shipments and returns of specimens, and necessary reminders:

- Loan number
- Deadline
- Number of reminders
- Number of items sent
- Number of items returned
- Number of types or figures sent
- Number of types or figures returned

This allows the manager to have a summary of the loans to that person and get an idea of the trust that can be given to that person for future loans.

4.4.3 - Visits by the requester

This section shows the list of visits by the requester to the MNHN's collections:

- Request number
- Actual start date of visit
- Actual end date of visit
- Total number of specimens/objects consulted during the visit
- Remarks

4.4.4 - List of requests made by the requester

This section shows all the requests made by the requester:

- Request ID
- Creation date
- Subject
- Type of request
- Service
- Collection
- Last action

4.5 - Institution page

When the name of the institution is clicked, a page appears containing all the information about the institution and the loans made by the institution.

Institution page

4.5.1 - Presentation of the institution

This section shows information about an institution:

- Name of the institution
- Address
- Postcode
- City
- Country

4.5.2 - Items on loan - expiration date has passed

This section shows a table containing specimens loaned and not returned on time, i.e. specimens loaned whose expiration date has passed. Collection managers can export this list as CSV file:

- Request number
- Inventory number
- Scientific name (Genus specific epithet)
- Returns: number of specimens returned /number of specimens loaned
- Loan expiration date
- Name of the requester
- Email of the requester
- Name of the collection manager in charge of the request
- Email of the collection manager in charge of the request

4.5.3 - Loans in progress

This section shows a list of loans in progress:

- Request number
- Expiration date
- Number of items sent
- Number of items returned
- Number of types or figures sent
- Number of types or figures returned

4.5.4 - Loans returned

This section shows a list of loans granted to the institution in which the specimens have been returned:

- Request number
- Expiration date
- Number of items sent
- Number of items returned
- Number of types or figures sent
- Number of types or figures returned

4.6 - The request page

When the request number is clicked, a page appears containing all the information about the request.

Request number XXX

Summary of the request number XXX

1 Information about the institution:
Name, address, postcode, city, country

Create a new request from it

Associated requests

2 List of associated requests

Loan

3.1 If the request is a loan:
Loan information

Items on loan

3.2 If the request is a loan:
list of specimens on loan

List of actions

4 List of actions carried out on request
by the managers

Possible actions

5 List of possible actions on request

Request page

4.6.1 - Summary of the request

This section contains information about the request and the requester:

- Name of the requester
- Type of the request
- Collection
- Subject
- Status
- Text
- Creation date
- Use
- Attachments

If the request is a loan extension, the following information is also indicated:

- Loan number
- Extension date

If the request is a visit, the following information is also indicated:

- Start date indicated by requester
- End date indicated by requester
- Actual start date of visit
- Actual end date of visit
- Remarks

If the request is a sampling request, the following information is also indicated:

- For commercial use (yes/no)

4.6.2 - Related requests

One request may be associated with another request. There are several processes that link two requests:

- It is possible to create a new request from a first request, so the new request will have the original request as a parent.
- A loan extension is also an extension of an initial loan request.

It is then possible to navigate between the associated requests.

4.6.3 - Loan

If the request is a loan, information about the loan is displayed:

- Loan number
- Expiration date
- Number of items returned / Number of items lent
- Notes loan slip

4.6.4 - Items loaned

If the request is a loan, the list of loaned specimens is displayed with the following information:

- Inventory number
- Scientific name (genus specific epithet)
- Returns: Number of specimens returned / number of specimens loaned
- Expiration date

4.6.5 - List of actions on the request

This section shows the list of actions carried out on the request, it is possible to group them by action type or sort them by date (default):

- Type of action
- Explanatory text of text of emails
- Date

4.7 - Actions on request

A collection manager in charge of the request can process the following actions.

4.7.1 - Communicate with the requester

The following actions involve communicating with the requester and sending an email to the requester.

Accept

Responding favourably to a request.

- 1 – The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Accept" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write a message.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database. If no message is provided, an automatic message will be used.
- 5 - The status of the request becomes "To be prepared."
- 6 - An automatic email is sent to the requester.
- 7 - An automatic email is sent to the collection manager who accepted the request.

Flowchart: Accept request

Refuse

Responding unfavourably to a request.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Refuse" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write a message.

- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database. If no message is provided, an automatic message will be used.
- 5 - The status of the request becomes "Close."
- 6 - An automatic email is sent to the requester.
- 7 - An automatic email is sent to the collection manager who refused the request.

Flowchart: Refuse request

Message

Send a message to the requester (no response required). The request continues to be examined with a view to its acceptance or refusal.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Message" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the manager to write a message.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database.
- 5 - An automatic email is sent to the requester.

Flowchart: Send message to requester

Request for information

Send a message to the requester (response required). The status of the request becomes "Pending" until the requester has responded.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Request for Information" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write a message.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database.
- 5 - The status of the request becomes "Pending."
- 6 - An automatic email is sent to the requester.
- 7 - The requester replies to the email with his preferred email client (sending email).
- 8 - The answer is recorded in database.
- 9 - The status of the request becomes "In progress".
- 10 - An automatic email is sent to the collection manager in charge of the request.

If the requester does not respond, it is possible to send a reminder to the requester by sending him a new message.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Reminder" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write a message.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database. If no message is provided, the previous message will be used.
- 5 - An automatic email is sent to the requester.

If the requester does not respond, it is possible to cancel the request for information.

- 1 - The manager in charge of the request clicks the "Cancel" button.
- 2 - Cancellation is recorded.
- 3 - The status of the request becomes "In progress."

Flowchart: Request for information

4.7.2 - Communicate between collection managers

The following actions enable communication between colleagues and keep a communications history.

Assign

Assign the request to a collection manager. The chosen collection manager will be the person in charge of the request.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Assign" button.
- 2 - The collection manager selects the new collection manager who will be the next person in charge of the request from a list of managers ranked by service.
- 3 - A form is provided to the manager to write a message.
- 4 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 5 - The message is recorded in database.
- 6 - The chosen collection manager is now in charge of the request.
- 7 - An automatic email is sent to the chosen collection manager.

Flowchart: Assign request

Comment

Add a comment to the request without changing the status of the request (informative).

- 1 - The collection manager clicks the "Comment" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write his comment.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The comment is recorded in database.

Flowchart: Comment request

Follow up

Send a message to a collection manager who follows the request without changing the status of the request.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Follow up" button.
- 2 - The collection manager selects another collection manager from a list of managers ranked by service.
- 3 - A form is provided to collection manager to write his message.
- 4 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 5 - The message is recorded in database.
- 6 - An automatic email is sent to the chosen collection manager.

Flowchart: Follow up

Request for advice

Send a message to a collection manager to ask for an advice. The status of the request becomes "Pending" as long as the colleague does not respond. The manager in charge of the request can send a reminder to the colleague or cancel the wait for the answer (the status becomes "In progress").

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Request for advice" button.
- 2 - The collection manager selects another collection manager from a list of collection managers ranked by service.
- 3 - A form is provided to collection manager to write his message.
- 4 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 5 - The message is recorded in database.
- 6 - The status of the request becomes "Pending."
- 7 - An automatic email is sent to the chosen collection manager.

If the collection manager (colleague) does not respond, it is possible to send a reminder by sending a new message.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Reminder" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write a message.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database. If no message is provided, the previous message will be used.
- 5 - An automatic email is sent to the collection manager who didn't respond.

If the manager does not respond, the request for advice can be cancelled.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Cancel" button.
- 2 - The cancellation of the request for advice is recorded.
- 3 - The status of the request becomes "In progress."

Flowchart: Follow up

Action

Send a message to a collection manager to request action while keeping responsibility for the request. The status of the request becomes "Pending" as long as the colleague does not respond.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Action" button.
- 2 - The collection manager selects a collection manager from a list of managers ranked by service.
- 3 - A form is provided to collection manager to write his message.
- 4 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 5 - The message is recorded in database.
- 6 - The status of the request becomes "Pending."
- 7 - An automatic email is sent to the chosen collection manager.

If the manager (colleague) does not respond, it is possible to send a reminder by sending a new message.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Reminder" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager to write a message.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The message is recorded in database. If no message is provided, the previous message will be used.
- 5 - An automatic email is sent to the collection manager who didn't respond.

If the manager does not respond, the request for action can be cancelled.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Cancel" button.
- 2 – The cancellation is recorded.
- 3 - The status of the request becomes "In progress."

Flowchart: Request for action

4.7.3 - Others actions

More specific actions are possible.

Close

Closing a request. Only accepted requests can be explicitly closed by this action. The request is thus archived.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Close" button.
- 2 - The status of the request becomes "close."

Flowchart: Close request

Assign to myself

Allow the dispatcher to be the person in charge of the request. This action is possible if the manager has a dispatcher role.

- 1 - The dispatcher clicks the "Assign to myself" button.
- 2 - The dispatcher becomes the new person in charge of the request.

Flowchart: Assign request to myself

Detail a visit

Add a comment on the visit and edit the actual dates of the visit.

- 1 - The collection manager in charge of the request clicks the "Detail the visit" button.
- 2 - A form is provided to the collection manager who can enter the actual dates of the visit (start date and end date) and a comment.
- 3 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 4 - The information is recorded in database.

The form contains three input fields: 'Actual start date of the visit', 'Actual end date of the visit', and 'Comment'. Below these fields is a 'Save' button.

Detail visit form

Detail a loan

Fill in information about the loan and associate specimens with request. This action allows you to have a clear colour code (red, green) in the loan sheet to find out if the loan to exceed the due date.

- 1 - The collection manager clicks the "Detail a Loan" button.
- 2 - The collection manager fills in the loan's expiration date.
- 3 - The collection manager fills in the loan's shipment date.
- 4 - The collection manager fills in the number of parcels sent.
- 5 - The collection manager can add comments which are used in the loan slip.
- 6 - The collection manager can associate one or more specimens with the loan request. The information about specimens are: inventory number, scientific name, country of origin, flags if specimen is a type or a figure, number of elements loaned (set of specimens without inventory numbers), comment about the specimen.
- 7 - The collection manager validates the form.
- 8 - The information is recorded in database.

Expiration Date

Shipment Date

Number of parcels sent

Comment

Specimens

Inventory number	Scientific name	Country of origin	Type	Figure	Number of specimen loaned	Comment
			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Detail loan form

Generate documents

Generate documents related to a loan for printing. These documents are:

- Loan slip: a document to be signed by the borrower at receipt of the loan and returned by post.
- Parcel label: a PDF document used to print a label stuck on the parcel.
- Envelope: a PDF document used to print a envelope sent to notify the borrower that loan is arriving soon.

1 – The collection manager clicks the “Generate documents” button.

2 – The collection manager chooses the type of document to generate.

3 – The collection manager prints the document.

Loan return

Record a partial or complete return of a loan with an indication of the status of the returned specimen ("good condition" or "damaged").

1 - The collection manager the request clicks the "Loan Return" button.

2 - The list of specimens is proposed to the collection manager with indications on the expiration date of the loan of the specimen (colour code).

3 - The collection manager lists the returned specimens by specifying the return date, the number of specimens returned (if set of specimens without inventory numbers) and the status of the returned specimen.

4 - The collection manager validates the form.

5 - The information is recorded in database.

5 - ELViS : Information and recommendation

Colhelper, a system created, managed and supplied by the MNHN's IT department, has seen its functionalities evolve since 2006, based mainly on feedback from collection managers.

As part of the work to define Colhelper's functionalities for the WP6 JRA1, a call for feedback from MNHN users was carried out, in order to identify what needs to be improved/modified to optimise Colhelper.

The information below is aimed at highlighting the points identified as important and desirable improvements in a collection access system such as ELViS.

5.1 - Organisation of services and managers

Requests sent via Colhelper are received by potentially 23 different dispatchers, who can transfer responsibility for the request to 341 collection managers.

Depending on the diversity of the collections, the specificities of the services and their own classifications of the collections, it seems important to allow institutions to be able to assign as many dispatchers and managers within their own institution.

5.2 - Front office for requesters

5.2.1 - Feedback on ORCID number

Feedback from the MNHNs consulted on the need for the creation of an ORCID number is unanimous as to the difficulty of imposing the creation of an identifier on another platform.

If this solution is adopted, it seems important to support it by explaining the need for this identification and facilitate its creation.

5.2.2 - List of requests

The MNHN has integrated different types of requests into Colhelper: loans, visits, sampling, image, exchange of material, donations/bequests/sales, exhibitions, questions about collections, moulding/preparation/restoration. These choices of types of requests meet the management needs of the MNHN's Collections Department. It would be useful if ELViS could allow for more than just visits and loan requests.

5.2.3 - General terms and conditions

The acceptance of requests is dependent on the requester's commitment to comply with general conditions per type of request which are defined by the MNHN and more specifically by the services. A system such as ELViS should allow the addition of general conditions per institution and per type of collection.

5.3 - Back office for collection managers

5.3.1 - Requalifying the request: Reassignment

A number of requesters make mistakes when choosing the type of request. In order to reassign the request, Colhelper allows you to create a new request from a previous request by correctly requalifying it so that the department concerned receives it. This action creates a new request.

In order to respond to this problem, it would be useful to provide for the possibility of requalification of a request by dispatchers and collection managers without rejecting the first and creating a second request.

5.3.2 - Requalifying the request: Changing the loan period

A missing functionality in Colhelper is the possibility for the manager to extend the loan period without having to create a new request for the requester.

5.4 - Communicate with the requester

5.4.1 - Automatic reply to requester

It would be advisable to send an email to the requester automatically after submission of a request indicating that the request has been registered and will be processed as soon as possible. This feature is not fundamental but is a matter of courtesy and avoids unnecessary solicitation of requesters.

5.4.2 - Automatic notifications

It would be interesting to add an automatic reminder to the person in charge of the request and to the dispatcher of the service by sending an email if a loan has come due. The system could also send an email to requester as a reminder of the loan due date.

The same applies to the sending of a notification to requesters in the event of a change in the loan period.

5.5 – Dashboard

As written previously, (see 4.1- Homepage), the manager on the home page of his Colhelper account has a view of the current, pending, to be prepared and closed requests.

However, the creation of a Dashboard with more information would be useful to improve the management and supervision of requests. This dashboard could provide statistics on requests and help to manage requests, especially loan requests.

For example, MNHN has developed an external dashboard to extract annual statistics by collection in order to produce an activity report for the institution. This functionality has to be included as an internal feature.

Loan requests are the most difficult to supervise and it would be useful to have a clear and concise picture of loans that are close to or past their expiration date. Collection managers will be able to see easily which requests need to be dealt with as a matter of priority.

The possibility of activating the sending of a report on current requests (e.g. monthly) to the managers on the requests that concern them would be a plus. This data could be extracted from this dashboard.

APPENDIX

APPENDIX A: General conditions for loans

National Museum of Natural History

General conditions for loans

The National Museum of Natural History makes specimens of its collections available to facilitate scientific research and knowledge dissemination. However, the MNHN requires from the applicant that he/she commits:

- to mention, in all publications or other supports, the name and inventory number of each specimen and explicitly mention “MNHN collection-Paris”.
- to mention “MNHN collection-Paris” in writing, in all uses with museographic, artistic and/or editorial goals, that the work was carried out based on the collections and/or the buildings.
- to send to the MNHN a duplicate of the publication or of any other support which quotes the specimen(s).

Responsibility for the material:

- the specimens are under the direct responsibility for the borrower, except for the students for whom the material is under the responsibility of the supervisor.
- the borrower can neither lend nor transfer the MNHN specimens to a third person or to another institute without prior authorization from the collection manager.

Conservation of the material:

The conditions under which specimens are conserved should under no circumstances affect their integrity.

- the borrower commits himself to restore the lent material in good condition and to return it carefully packed up, within, and not later than, the agreed loan period.
- the borrower or his/her institution is responsible for any damage to borrowed specimens until such a time as they are returned to the MNHN.
- the return of type specimens must be done by secured means.
- any request for the prolongation of a loan requires the written permission of the collection manager.

Specificity MAMMALS and BIRDS

- the specimens must be kept safe from light and destructive insects (mites and dermestres).
- when returning the material, the original packing material must be re-used.

BOTANICAL specificity

- the material must be stored in a dry room safe from any insect infestation.
- the use of cellulose adhesive or adhesive tape is strictly prohibited.

CITES:

The borrower, as the MNHN, is committed to observing the procedures of authorization of circulation of the specimens concerned by the Washington Convention (CITES).

Determination of specimens:

- The original labels should neither be modified, nor removed.
- In the case of a correction or confirmation of the specimen determination, its name, that of the determinator and the date of determination must be registered on an additional label.
- If the loan should contain types of new taxa, the latter will have to be deposited and registered with the inventory of MNHN-Paris.

Inalienable property of the MNHN:

- All of the lent specimens must be returned to the MNHN.
- All the detached fragments, even those detached accidentally, must be reported and the fragments placed close to the carefully packed specimen.
- **Neither sampling for molecular, anatomical or palynological studies, nor preparations (dissection, colouring, moulding...) can be made without prior permission from the curator. A separate request will have to be formulated on the Requests on the Collections of MNHN website.**

Specific conditions in the event of authorization of sampling and/or preparation:

- **All of the prepared material and the remainders not used must be returned to the MNHN and, if possible, an aliquot of the DNA extractions. Upon their return, the preparations must accompany the corresponding specimens: specific packing, clear annotation.**
- When sampling, the smallest quantity of useful material will be taken from that part of the specimen where sampling will be least destructive.
- When slides are prepared, it is to be envisaged that duplicate preparations will be sent to the MNHN collections.

Specificity PALAEONTOLOGY

- Material that is released using acid must be transported manually after being fixed in polyethylene glycol.

Specificity MAMMALS & BIRDS

- Sampling will be carried out at the MNHN, and not on borrowed specimens. In this case it will be necessary to put in a request for the sampling of material.

Images:

The taking of pictures (photography, radiography, digitalization) is authorized under certain conditions:

- the conditions for making images will have to guarantee the maintenance of the specimen in good condition.
- a duplicate of each image, the legend of which will specify the name of the specimen concerned and its inventory number, will have to be given to the manager of the MNHN's photographic library.
- no commercial use (including a derived use) can be made of the image without a preliminary authorization request that will be transmitted to the Communication service of MNHN (DICAP), for which a fee or duty could be requested.
- the MNHN is committed make apparent all necessary legal acknowledgements including the name of the author if it uses these images.

Contention:

The non-observance of any of these instructions or the conditions of consultation is likely to result in restrictions on future loans, including the possibility that further loans may not be approved.

APPENDIX B: General conditions for sampling of material

National Museum of Natural History

General conditions for **sampling of material**

Within the context of a request for sampling:

- sampling will be carried out at the MNHN, and not on borrowed specimens.
- the sampling will be controlled by an agent of the MNHN.
- the results will be transmitted to the MNHN, even in the case of negative results.

The National Museum of Natural History makes specimens of its collections available to facilitate scientific research and knowledge dissemination. However, the MNHN requires from the applicant that he/she commits:

- to mention, in all publications or other supports, the name and inventory number of each specimen and explicitly mention "MNHN collection -Paris".
- to mention "MNHN collection -Paris" in writing, in all uses with museographic, artistic and/or editorial goals, that the work was carried out based on the collections and/or the buildings.
- to send to the MNHN a duplicate of the publication or of any other support which quotes the specimen(s).

Specificity MAMMALS & BIRDS

- Sampling will be controlled by an agent of the MNHN and will be limited to a single sample per specimen.

CITES:

The borrower, as the MNHN, is committed to observing the procedures of authorization of circulation of the specimens concerned by the Washington Convention (CITES).

Contention:

The non-observance of any of these instructions is likely to result in restrictions on future loans, including the possibility that further loans may not be approved.

APPENDIX C: General conditions for the exchange of material

National Museum of Natural History

General conditions for the exchange of material

The National Museum of Natural History makes the specimens of its collections available to facilitate scientific research and knowledge dissemination. However, the MNHN requires from the applicant that he/she commits:

- to mention, in all publications or other supports, the name and inventory number of each specimen and explicitly mention "MNHN collection -Paris".
- to mention "MNHN collection -Paris" in writing, in all uses with museographic, artistic and/or editorial goals, that the work was carried out based on the collections and/or the buildings.
- to send to the MNHN a duplicate of the publication or of any other support which quotes the specimen(s).

The material belonging to the patrimonial collections of the MNHN benefit from a legal protection in agreement with the rights of museums.

For this reason, only the material not catalogued MNHN, under the museums law, can be the subject of an exchange.

CITES:

The borrower, as the MNHN, is committed to observing the procedures of authorization of circulation of specimens in line with the Washington Convention (CITES).

Contention:

The non-observance of these instructions is likely to result in restrictions at the time of future loans, including the possibility that further loans may not be approved.

APPENDIX D: General conditions for the use of images

National Museum of Natural History

General conditions for the use of images

The National Museum of Natural History makes images of specimens from its collections available (photography, radiography, digitalization) to facilitate scientific research and the dissemination of knowledge. The MNHN requires however, that users commit:

- to mention, in all publications or other supports, the name and inventory number of each specimen and explicitly mention “MNHN collection-Paris”.
- to mention “MNHN collection-Paris” in writing, in all uses with museographic, artistic and/or editorial goals, that the work was carried out based on the collections and/or the buildings.
- to send to the MNHN a duplicate of the publication or of any other support which quotes the specimen(s).
- to make no commercial use (including a derived use) of the images without a request for authorization that will be transmitted to the Communication service of MNHN (DICAP), in which case a duty/fee could be requested.

Contention:

The non-observance of these instructions is likely to result in restrictions at the time of future loans, including the possibility that further loans may not be approved.

APPENDIX E: General conditions for visits

National Museum of Natural History

General conditions for

visits to consult the collections

The National Museum of Natural History makes specimens of its collections available to facilitate scientific research and knowledge dissemination. However, the MNHN requires from the applicant that he/she commits:

- to mention, in all publications or other supports, the name and inventory number of each specimen and explicitly mention “MNHN collection -Paris”.
- to mention “MNHN collection -Paris” in writing, in all uses with museographic, artistic and/or editorial goals, that the work was carried out based on the collections and/or the buildings.
- to send to the MNHN a duplicate of the publication or of any other support which quotes the specimen(s).

Visits are granted according to the availability of the MNHN personnel and available space.

The visitor engages:

- to respect the instructions specific to the visited collection.
- to conform to all measures of order, policing and monitoring of the MNHN.
- to respect the schedules which will have been indicated.
- to subscribe to solvent companies the insurance policies whose object is to guarantee all the consequences of the risks that incur or may incur to the objects and the places as a result of the activities and presence of the visitor.

Conservation of the material:

- the visitor or his institution is responsible for any damage to specimens.

BOTANICAL specificity

- The use of cellulose adhesive or adhesive tape is strictly prohibited.

Determination of the specimens:

- the original labels should be neither modified, nor removed.
- In the case of a correction or confirmation of the specimen determination, its name, that of the determinator and the date of determination must be registered on an additional label.

Inalienable property of the MNHN:

- All of the detached fragments, even those detached accidentally, must be mentioned and placed close to the specimen concerned and carefully packed.
- **No sampling for molecular, anatomical or palynologic studies, nor any preparation (dissection, colouring, moulding...) can be made without prior agreement from the person in charge. A separate request will have to be formulated on the Requests on the Collections of MNHN-website.**

Special conditions relating to the authorization of sampling and/or preparation:

- **All of the prepared material and those remainders not used must be returned to the MNHN and, if possible, an aliquot of the DNA extraction. Upon return of material, the preparations must accompany the corresponding specimens: specific packaging, clear annotations.**

Specificity PALAEONTOLOGY

- Material that is released using acid must be transported manually after being fixed in polyethylene glycol.

Specificity MAMMALS & BIRDS

- Sampling will be controlled by an agent of the MNHN and will be limited to a single sample per specimen.

- Results will be transmitted to the MNHN, even in the case of negative results.

Images:

The taking of pictures (photography, radiography, digitalization) is authorized under certain conditions:

- the conditions for making images will have to guarantee the maintenance of the specimen in good condition.
- a duplicate of each image, the legend of which will specify the name of the specimen concerned and its inventory number, will have to be given to the manager of the MNHN's photographic library.
- no commercial use (including a derived use) can be made of the image without a preliminary authorization request that will be transmitted to the Communication service of MNHN (DICAP), for which a fee or duty could be requested.
- the MNHN is committed make apparent all necessary legal acknowledgements including the name of the author if it uses these images.
- **the curator of the collection reserves the right to refuse the taking of images if the conditions of the latter are incompatible with the maintenance in good condition of the specimen concerned.**

Contention:

The non-observance of any of these instructions or the conditions of consultation is likely to result in restrictions on future visits, including the possibility that further visits may not be approved.

